

IMPROVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN THE AGRICULTURAL ECONOMY

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Abstract. *In order to determine the effectiveness of agricultural electrification, this article highlights the important aspects of the use of energy resources in agriculture and labor productivity in the use of electricity in grain.*

Key words: *agricultural electrification, labor productivity, product cost, 1 man-hour, net income, lighting, heating greenhouses, water, pump, electrification of stations, stationary, portable irrigation, electrification of aggregates, hatcheries.*

INTRODUCTION

Energy is one of the main sectors of every economy and is a solid foundation of economic and technical development. The energy system of Uzbekistan consists of 37 thermal and hydraulic power plants with a total installed capacity of 11.5 mln. kW, 55 billion per year. It has the ability to generate more than 100 kW of electricity. The total length of electric networks of all voltages of the energy system of Uzbekistan is about 228 thousand km. The total capacity of network transformers is 42.6 MVA. About 65,000 people work in the energy system of the republic. On September 25, 1934, the organizational base of the energy system of Uzbekistan, the "Uzbekenergiya" energy department (now the Ministry of Energy and Electrification of the Republic of Uzbekistan) was established.

Currently, the energy system of Uzbekistan provides energy to more than 20,000 industrial, 100,000 agricultural, 20,000 communal and 3.5 million household consumers. The total electricity consumption in the republic is 46.1 billion. kW is an hour. Hydropower. The total installed capacity of 27 HPPs in the energy system

of Uzbekistan is 1420 MW. They have 6331.2 mln. kWh of electricity is being produced.

In the development of hydropower in Uzbekistan, the design and construction of hydroelectric power stations in the Pskom River, Topalang, Hisarak, and Akhangaron reservoirs is in the leading position. Heat energy. In the 1960s, the increase in electricity generation in the republic was mainly carried out in the direction of launching large gas-fired thermal power plants. As a result of the construction of large thermal power plants, the installed capacity of the energy system of Uzbekistan reached 11.3 thousand MW.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

As in all sectors of the national economy, the supply and use of electricity is of great importance in agriculture. In agriculture, electricity is mainly used for lighting, heating, that is, electrification of greenhouses, water pumping stations, electrification of stationary and mobile irrigation units, creation of microclimate in hatcheries and livestock farms, etc. The problems of using the quality of initial indicators to determine the effectiveness of agricultural electrification are currently relevant.

The initial indicators for determining the efficiency of agricultural electrification are the following: the production of agricultural products by crops on the land area and plowed land in kind and at the expense of money; production of livestock products in terms of their number according to the type of animals and in terms of money; the number and power of electric motors, electrical devices, devices by sectors and processes, the cost of electrification means (substations, power transmission networks, mechanisms), annual energy consumption by all economic sectors, the cost of 1 kW of power, the number of service personnel, labor costs before and after electrification for the production of agricultural products, the availability of electricity to farms, all these characterize the possibilities of electrification of production processes.

As long as the construction of power transmission networks and distribution and production facilities is solid and guaranteed, not only agriculture, but all sectors of the national economy will be ensured to function effectively. The role of this network in agriculture is very important because, firstly, it ensures continuous operation of water lifting devices in processes related to crop irrigation, and secondly, certain types of cultivated products are kept intact in warehouses and refrigerators. In addition, the power transmission network has its effect in increasing the quality and quantity of the products grown in the livestock industry or in the poultry industry in the process of using electricity. Full electrification of agricultural production increases labor productivity and reduces production costs.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Construction of power plants shortens the payback period for electricity supply and improves the living conditions of rural residents. Fully electrifying agriculture improves the quality of crops and reduces the demand for labor. The use of electric energy in agriculture creates the possibility of mechanization of crop irrigation, reducing labor costs by 10-20% and operating costs by 10%. The use of electricity for heating and lighting greenhouses, and for running water pumps not only reduces labor costs, but also increases the yield per hectare of cultivated land. A product worth 100-150 soums is created for each soum of electricity.

The use of electricity in grain farming increases labor productivity 3-4 times. The use of "OS-1", "OS-3", "OB-10" grain cleaning mechanisms in grain production reduces labor costs by 20-25%, and product costs by 1535%. During grain drying, the labor cost is reduced by 30-40%, and the cost is reduced by 20-35%.

The use of electricity in animal husbandry leads to a sharp reduction in labor costs. The use of electricity can be used to perform a number of activities on the farm, including water supply, advance provision of feed to animals, milking cows, transportation of various loads, sheep shearing, preliminary processing of milk, incubation, etc. with the help of mechanization. allows to perform.

Automation of irrigation works increases the productivity of livestock by 10-15% and improves the quality of the obtained product. The use of electricity in the preliminary preparation of fodder for cattle reduces labor costs by 75-90% and improves the quality of fodder. Electrification of cattle milking is also of great importance. In addition to saving labor costs when milking cows using milking machines, the work of milkers is also lightened. 1 s. 4.4 man-hours are used for milking by hand, 2.5 man-hours for milking with a milking machine, and 1.8 man-hours for milking in a milking parlor. The use of electricity in animal husbandry not only saves milking labor, but also increases the purity of milk.

Shearing sheep's wool with the help of mechanisms increases labor productivity by 3-4 times, and the quality of the sheared wool is much higher. As a result of lighting poultry farms at night with electricity, eggs from chickens and ducks increase by 25-30 percent. The use of electric energy in auxiliary branches of the economy, including workshops, mills, wood sawing, etc., gives great economic benefits. According to research institutes, every billion kWh of electricity used in agriculture saves the labor of 700,000 able-bodied people per year and reduces production costs by 2 million. reduces to soum. The use of electricity plays a major role in improving the material and cultural well-being of the rural population, bringing the rural culture closer to the urban culture.

DISCUSSION

Effective use of electricity in agriculture is determined by the following indicators: labor productivity, product cost, net income per person per hour, income per 1 soum of production costs, profitability, additional capital expenditure return period.

6% of energy resources and 27% of electricity are consumed in the branches of the agro-industrial complex, which produce more than 32% of the republic's gross domestic product. Although these indicators are several times lower than in

developed countries, the energy capacity of product production remains high. There are objective and subjective reasons for this situation.

CONCLUSION

The main production funds, equipment and technologies in such a field are outdated. A new energy and electrotechnological equipment system based on fundamental scientific research has not been formed. Most of these equipments and technologies do not fully meet the demand. There are problems with their use, repair, adjustment and retraining of personnel. Based on the specific characteristics of agriculture, it is necessary to conduct fundamental and scientific-technical research and develop organizational-technical measures in this branch of the economy, including the following areas related to the basics of efficient use of energy and the creation of energy-saving equipment and technologies:

- development of a single program of the state energy policy aimed at the development of the agrarian sector and coordination of scientific research related to its implementation, organization of a scientific and technical team consisting of mature experts and scientists of the field;
- assessment of efficiency of use of energy resources, including electricity, in production, processing and storage of products, creation of methodological bases, and in this regard energy resources and consumers are interrelated in a single system.

To overcome these and other problems, to achieve an increase in gross production in the sectors of the agro-industrial complex by finding a solution, seed production, breeding development, increasing soil fertility, improving land reclamation and other agrotechnical measures, together with low productivity, high instead of manual labor it is necessary to create efficient, energy-saving equipment, to accelerate technological processes, to use electrophysical effects directly in work processes, which ensure the achievement of new technological results. Also, special attention should be paid to the use of non-traditional types of energy, i.e. "Solar energy", in order to increase the weight of energy in product production .

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